

Investigating the Perceptions of EFL Teachers towards ELF: The Role of Teaching Experience

Fikri GECKİNLİ^{*a}, Cevdet YILMAZ^b

Article Info

DOI:

Article History:

Received 06.04.2021

Revised 28.04.2021

Accepted 25.05.2021

Keywords:

English as a Lingua Franca,
EFL Teachers,
Teachers' Perceptions.

Article Type:

Research Article

Abstract

The paradigm of English as a lingua franca (ELF) suggests that the contemporary status of English as a global medium of communication requires some changes not only in the perception of this language but also in English language pedagogy. Since EFL teachers are the ones who are responsible for incorporating what is new into ELT classroom, how they feel about all these developments becomes a critical issue. For that reason, this particular study concentrated on less experienced and experienced EFL teachers' perceptions of ELF and its pedagogical implications. The data were collected using a questionnaire from 32 less experienced and 20 experienced EFL teachers teaching at university English preparatory program. Findings revealed that the less experienced EFL teachers had a greater awareness of the concept of ELF than the experienced EFL teachers did. However, both the less experienced and the experienced EFL teachers were neutral when it comes to the implications this concept suggests for ELT classroom.

İngilizceyi Yabancı Dil Olarak Öğreten Öğretmenlerin İngilizcenin Lingua Franca Olması Hakkındaki Algıları: Tecrübenin Önemi

Makale Bilgisi

DOI:

Makale Geçmişi:

Geliş 06.04.2021

Düzeltilme 28.04.2021

Kabul 25.05.2021

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Ortak İletişim Dili Olarak
İngilizce,
İngilizce Öğretmenleri,
Öğretmen Algıları.

Makale Türü:

Araştırma Makalesi

Öz

İngilizcenin uluslararası bir iletişim dili olmasına dair (ELF) paradigma bu dilin statüsünün algılanışına ve pedagojisine ilişkin bazı değişikliklere gidilmesi gerektiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Bu değişiklikleri sınıfa aktaracak olan başlıca aktörler de İngilizce öğretmenleridir. Dolayısıyla onların tüm bu gelişmeler hakkındaki algıları kritik bir önem arz etmektedir. Bu çerçevede bu araştırma deneyimli ve az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin ELF ve onun pedagojik sonuçlarına dair algılarını karşılaştırmalı olarak incelemiştir. Veriler, bir üniversitenin İngilizce hazırlık okulunda çalışan 32 az deneyimli ve 20 deneyimli İngilizce öğretmeninden nicel araştırma yöntemi kullanılarak toplanmıştır. Bulgular, az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İngilizcenin uluslararası bir iletişim dili olması statüsüne dair daha fazla farkındalığa sahip olduklarını ortaya koymuştur. Diğer yandan, bu kavramın pedagojik sonuçlarının sınıf içinde uygulanmasına gelindiğinde, hem deneyimli hem de az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenleri kararsız bir tutum sergilemişlerdir.

*Corresponding Author: fgeckinli@gmail.com

^a Lecturer, İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim University, İstanbul/Turkey, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3572-5939>

^b Prof. Dr., Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Çanakkale/Turkey <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4713-6565>

Introduction

Kachru (1985), in three concentric circles, characterized proliferation of English around the world. Nonetheless, due to the movement of people from one country to another, the borders described by the model were blurred which made this categorization weak. This model basically consists of countries in which English is spoken as a mother tongue, those colonized by English speaking countries in the past, and the ones in which English is taught and learned as a foreign language (Miyagi, 2006). The unprecedented expansion of English around the world was also conceptualized with some other terms, such as English as an international language (EIL), World Englishes (WE), as well as English as a lingua franca (ELF) which is the focus of the existing research. Jenkins (2006) identified ELF as the adoption of English as a common medium of communication by the speakers from various linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Likewise, Bayyurt and Dewey (2020) describes it as a versatile conception adopted by both native and non-native English speakers from assorted backgrounds.

English language has undergone some structural and functional changes as a result of its widespread use around the world and the number of its non-native speakers. Most of the international contacts between the speakers of different first languages are conducted in English (Matsuda, 2003). In this case, enforcing native English norms in English language teaching turns out to be irrelevant (Matsuda, 2003). Instead, bringing varieties of English to learners' attention becomes more relevant due to the greater need for international communication (Miyagi, 2006). Moreover, learners' needs to express their identities as well as their social and cultural actualities entail a more international perspective on English language teaching. Jenkins (2006) states that knowledge and endorsement of varieties of English are likely to have a positive impact on learners' own use of English.

Pursuit of standard English

Learning and using the so-called standard form of English has always been a pursuit in English language teaching and learning. Language is fetishized through standardization and using it in assessment based on native rules (Stilley, 1997). Standardized form of language does not represent a specific group of people speaking it, rather it represents the printed form of a language (Sato, 1989). American and British versions of English have been dominant models in English pedagogy over many years (He & Zhang, 2010). The widespread use of English in the world has not changed this situation much though. Nevertheless, the idea that non-native English varieties can be the part of English language education has also been thriving for some time (Algeo, 1993).

Considering language as an unchanging phenomenon can be convenient in a lot of ways; nevertheless, it does not represent the reality. On the contrary, being in a constant state of change is an inherent reality of language. Language is used in multiple ways depending on the context of the communication and who we are interacting with. Hence, an unconventional conceptualization of language as a dynamic and variable phenomenon becomes a critical requirement (Canagarajah, 2007). Additionally, language variation is a particularly justifiable concept for English language due to its status as a global medium of communication. This variation can range from how an individual uses the language to how it is used nationwide (Miyagi, 2006).

Teachers' preference for standard English

For many English teachers, teaching multiple varieties of English is likely to be a cause for apprehension in educational methodologies. To illustrate, for EFL teachers shifting from teaching native English norms to teaching a language including various cultures and varieties can be intimidating (Bruthiaux, 2010). Also, high-stake exams continue to reinforce the leading position of native English varieties in the countries where English is taught as a foreign language. For example, native English oriented exams and textbooks are preferred choice in Japan in spite of everything (Matsuda, 2003). Hence, predominant position of native English models in ELT market stands as leading cause for EFL teachers to stick with them in English classroom (Miyagi, 2006). However, it would serve better to the needs of the learners when the priority was given to the international use of English in ELT (He & Zhang, 2010).

As an indication of EFL teachers' choice of native English as teaching model, in a study conducted with 36 in-service and 28 pre-service Japanese English teachers, most of the participants expressed that they opted for native English as a model in their lessons (Miyagi, 2006). In another study conducted by He and Zhang (2010) majority of the students and the teachers stated that they were not concerned by the mother tongue influence in their English accents although teachers advocated native-like English accent for their students. Likewise, studies conducted in Turkish context revealed EFL teachers' preference for native English norms in their classes despite their awareness of ELF (Bayyurt, 2008; Coskun, 2011; İncecay & Akyel, 2014; Soruc, 2015; Zabitgil Gülseren & Sarıca, 2020).

However, a project conducted by Bayyurt and Sifakis (2015) with some in-service English teachers revealed that raising their awareness regarding English as a lingua franca increased their self-confidence as non-native English teachers and encouraged them to experiment some activities compatible with ELF perspective with their students in their lessons. Likewise, Biricik Deniz, Kemaloglu-Er, and Ozkan (2020) discovered that pre-service EFL teachers tend to incorporate ELF in their pedagogical practices once their awareness is raised. Also, Soruç and Griffiths (2021) observed how prospective EFL teachers' viewpoints changed in line with ELF perspective following some tasks aiming to raise their awareness of ELF.

All things considered, English pedagogy needs to be restructured in line with the changing circumstances as regards this language. In order for this adaptation to be realized, EFL teachers become known as prominent actors due to their critical positions between what is being theorized in ELT and translated into English classroom. Therefore, their perceptions towards newly emerging conceptualizations of English language are of primary significance since they are in a position to influence their students' language production immediately. Revealing tertiary level Turkish EFL teachers' perceptions towards ELF and its pedagogical implications can facilitate to prepare a more representative language program.

Literature suggests that the more time teachers spend in their professions, the more old-fashioned they are likely to become in their views about their teaching practices (Veenman, 1984). Nevertheless, the current status of English requires a more international perspective on English language teaching. From this standpoint, investigating EFL teachers' perceptions in relation to the number of years they have spent in teaching English is worthwhile in order to obtain their most recent views regarding ELF and its pedagogical implications. Moreover, there are not many studies comparing less experienced and experienced teachers' perceptions in that regard. The results are also likely to contribute to the literature in terms of revealing the extent to which current education prepares teachers with regard to ELF principles and whether the experienced teachers require more or less training on the same principles.

To this end, following research questions were devised to address the previously mentioned issue:

- (1) Do the perceptions of Turkish EFL teachers towards ELF change according to their years of teaching experience?
- (2) Do the perceptions of Turkish EFL teachers change according to their years of teaching experience regarding the factors: English varieties, ELF features, and English learning objectives?
- (3) Do the perceptions of Turkish EFL teachers towards the pedagogical implications of ELF change according to their years of teaching experience?
- (4) Do the perceptions of Turkish EFL teachers change according to their years of teaching experience regarding the factors: English teachers, target language culture, global cultures, and English exams?

Method

Research Design

This part of the study encompasses specifics about setting and participants, data collection tools, data collection procedure and analysis. The study was designed based on the exploitation of survey model since an existing situation was being investigated (Karasar, 2014). In view of that, this research design describes the understandings of the participants with numbers hence quantifiable data are obtained to make use of in the study (Creswell, 2014).

Setting and Participants

This research was conducted at a foundation university where English was used as a medium of instruction as it hosted international students and academics. Moreover, English was often used as a chosen means of communication between these students and academics who came from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Additionally, at this university, studying at English preparatory program was compulsory for the students who could not pass the proficiency exam held by the university before they commenced their courses in their departments. Therefore, EFL teachers' views regarding the changing face of English as a lingua franca of international contacts emerged as a topic worthy of investigation in such a multilingual context. Put it more precisely, teachers in the English preparatory program of this university was targeted as a research population. In total, 52 EFL teachers participated in the study. Regarding their practical experiences of teaching English, while the number of teachers with 1-5 years (less experienced) of teaching experience was 32, the number of the teachers with over 5 years (experienced) of teaching experience was 20. Among the departments they graduated from were English Language Teaching, English Language Literature, English language and interpretation, American Language Literature, and Linguistics.

Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire used in this research was previously published in the researcher's doctoral thesis (Geçkinli, 2020). A questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the relevant literature (Deniz, Özkan & Bayyurt, 2016; Jenkins, 2015; Soruc, 2015; İnceçay & Akyel, 2014; Cogo & Dewey, 2012; Coskun, 2011; Seidlhofer, 2011; Ton & Pham, 2010) and adopting five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" was used to collect the required data in this study. While preparing the questionnaire, the researcher paid regard to the most prominent issues discussed in the relevant literature and the intended population. After the piloting, the result obtained for Cronbach's Alpha reliability was sufficient (.71) to go ahead with the necessary analyses (George & Mallery, 2003). The questionnaire was devised in English initially and translated into Turkish with the assumption that participants would respond to the items more efficiently. In the first section, participants were asked to provide demographic information including their genders and years of teaching experience. In the second part, with an aim of finding an answer to the first and second research questions, their perceptions regarding the concept of ELF was sought after with 13 items constituting 3 sub-dimensions (English varieties, ELF features, and English learning objectives). Likewise, intending to explore the third and fourth research questions, the last section of the questionnaire considered the participants' perceptions towards the pedagogical implications of ELF with 13 items comprising 4 sub-dimensions (English teachers, target language culture, global cultures, and English exams).

Data Collection and Analysis

In this study, convenience sampling was applied as a sampling methodology. After the necessary permissions were taken from the university and the head of the English preparatory program, the researcher scheduled an appropriate time with the EFL teachers for conducting the questionnaire. Then the printed questionnaires were distributed to the teachers by the researcher which lasted for about half an hour for them to answer and submit. A total of 52 teachers returned the questionnaires by responding to the items applicably. In order to analyse the data collected in this study, inferential statistics were applied to the results employing SPSS 25. Independent sample t-tests were utilized to reveal the possible similarities and differences between less experienced and experienced EFL teachers. Within this framework, the first five years of a teachers' professional life is considered to be the period in which teachers are inexperienced (Sharabyan, 2011). Some items regarding the concept of ELF as well as the pedagogical implications of ELF were reverse coded in favour of ELF perspective so as to obtain aggregate results concerning the perceptions of EFL teachers. Thus, the results made it possible to compare the views of these two groups.

Findings

The first research question investigated whether EFL teachers' perceptions towards English as a lingua franca vary according to their years of teaching experience. To this end, the quantitatively collected data were analysed by making use of independent sample t-tests.

Table 1. Independent Samples T-test Results of EFL Teachers' Perceptions towards ELF Based on their Years of Teaching Experience

	Experience (Years)	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
EFL Teachers' Perceptions towards ELF	1-5	32	3.69	.50	3.231	50	.002*
	Over 5	20	3.23	.50			

* $p \leq .05$

Table 1 shows the independent sample t-test results of less experienced (1-5 years of experience) and experienced (over 5 years of experience) EFL teachers' perceptions towards ELF. As outlined in the table, the results indicate noteworthy variations between the two groups of teachers with reference to their perceptions towards ELF from the point of their professional experience. In accordance with this situation, the corresponding p value is below 0.05 ($p = .002$) and the mean scores substantiating these findings are $M1 = 3.69$ for less experienced teachers and $M2 = 3.23$ for experienced teachers.

The second research question aimed to expand the first one and scrutinized whether EFL teachers' perceptions towards ELF construct differ according to their years of teaching experience in terms of the factors: varieties of English, ELF features, and English learning objectives. In line with this objective, the quantitatively collected data were analysed by making use of independent sample t-tests.

Table 2. Teachers' Perceptions towards the Factors about ELF According to their Years of Teaching Experience

Factors	Experience (Years)	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Varieties of English	1-5	32	3.92	.77	2.762	50	.008*
	Over 5	20	3.36	.58			
ELF Features	1-5	32	3.85	.59	2.033	50	.047*
	Over 5	20	3.46	.78			
English Learning Objectives	1-5	32	3.28	.75	2.225	50	.031*
	Over 5	20	2.82	.69			

* $p \leq .05$

Table 2 illustrates independent sample t-test results about the factors (varieties of English, ELF features, and English learning objectives) constituting the questionnaire about ELF construct in relation to the views of less experienced and experienced EFL teachers. Pertaining to the above-mentioned factors, the consequences reveal significant differences in what concerns the perceptions of less experienced teachers as against the experienced ones. The resultant p values and the mean scores for the factors are as follows: varieties of English $p1 = .008$, $M1 = 3.92$, $M2 = 3.36$; ELF features $p2 = .047$, $M3 = 3.85$, $M4 = 3.46$; English learning objectives $p3 = .031$, $M5 = 3.28$, $M6 = 2.82$ respectively.

As the data in Table 1 and Table 2 suggest, less experienced EFL teachers display a more favorable attitude towards ELF as a concept in comparison to the experienced EFL teachers. Stated in other words,

English teachers with maximum five years of teaching experience tend to be more flexible towards the variations in English language in relation to its position as a vehicular language between the speakers from various linguistic backgrounds in numerous domains of life such as trade, tourism, aviation, academia just to name a few.

The third research question examined whether EFL teachers' perceptions towards the pedagogical implications of English as a lingua franca diverge according to their years of teaching experience. This being the case, the quantitatively collected data were analysed by making use of independent sample t-tests.

Table 3. Independent Samples T-test Results of EFL Teachers' Perceptions towards the Pedagogical Implications of ELF Based on their Years of Teaching Experience

	Experience (Years)	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Perceptions towards the Pedagogical Implications of ELF	1-5	32	3.44	.45	.792	50	.432
	Over 5	20	3.33	.54			

* $p \leq .05$

Table 3 shows the independent sample t-test results of English teachers' perceptions towards the pedagogical implications of ELF with respect to their teaching experience in years. As can be observed in the data, the consequences do not specify any significant variations in that sense between the perceptions of less experienced and experienced EFL teachers in relation to their professional backgrounds. Accordingly, the associated p value introducing this outcome is above 0.05 ($p = .432$) and the mean scores confirming these results are $M1 = 3.44$ for less experienced EFL teachers and $M2 = 3.33$ for experienced EFL teachers.

The fourth research question intended to expand the third one and inspected whether EFL teachers' perceptions towards the pedagogical implications of ELF change according to their years of teaching experience regarding the factors: English teachers, English exams, Target language cultures, and global cultures. In consideration of the foregoing, the quantitatively collected data were analysed by consuming independent sample t-tests.

Table 4. Teachers' Perceptions towards the Factors about Pedagogical Implications of ELF According to their Years of Teaching Experience

Factors	Experience (Years)	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
English Teachers	1-5	32	3.15	.55	-1.435	50	.666
	Over 5	20	3.24	.83			
English Exams	1-5	32	3.53	.86	1.182	50	.243
	Over 5	20	3.23	.88			
Target Language Culture	1-5	32	3.50	.83	.336	50	.738
	Over 5	20	3.42	.69			
Global Cultures	1-5	32	3.96	.75	1.149	50	.256
	Over 5	20	3.70	.92			

* $p \leq .05$

Table 4 exhibits the results as concerns the factors constituting the pedagogical implications of ELF. The obtained outcomes do not disclose any substantial divergences between the views of less experienced and experienced English teachers in connection with the given factors. To this end, associated p values as well as the mean scores corresponding to each factor are as follows: English teachers $p1 = .666, M1 = 3.15, M2 = 3.24$; English exams $p2 = .243, M3 = 3.53, M4 = 3.23$; target language culture: $p3 = .738, M5 = 3.50, M6 = 3.42$; global cultures: $p4 = .256, M7 = 3.96, M8 = 3.70$ respectively.

With reference to the data displayed in Table 3 and Table 4, it can be concluded that less experienced as well as experienced teachers are hesitant when it comes to the pedagogical implications of ELF in ELT classroom. In other words, EFL teachers, irrespective of their experiences in their teaching careers, seem to be under the dominant influence of standard English ideology which possibly leads them to be in a dilemma pertaining to applying ELF in their classes.

Discussion

At the outset, while the first question of this research looked at the overall perceptions of EFL teachers towards the concept of ELF according to their years of teaching experience, the second research question elaborated on the subcategories (varieties of English, ELF features, and English learning objectives) of the same concept. To this end, the outcomes indicate a considerable variation between two groups of teachers. Accordingly, less experienced teachers exhibited a more constructive approach about lingua franca position of English. Given that they acknowledge being familiarized with non-standard Englishes as reported by the data in this study, they can see that standard English is not the only choice in international contacts that they can make use of. As for the experienced English teachers, in comparison to less experienced English teachers, they subscribe less to the notions suggested by ELF concept. In line with these, Cogo and Dewey, (2012) and Jenkins (2007) likewise accentuate the existence of a difference held by less experienced and experienced English teachers towards ELF.

It can be said that less experienced English teachers are more willing to recognize the status of English as global lingua franca. This might be due to the fact that these teachers' beliefs about English pedagogy are not nearly as deep-rooted as of the experienced ones due to the shorter period of time they spent in the profession. Furthermore, increasing popularity of social networking websites along with an opportunity for participation to student exchange programs such as Erasmus might have given a chance to less experienced teachers to come into contact with some indigenous varieties of English (Lee, 2009; Kalocsai, 2009). Also, thanks to the programs such as Erasmus, they realize it is not a bare necessity to speak with a flawless grammar (Kaypak & Ortactepe, 2014). As a consequence, all these encounters with non-native usages of English might have increased their awareness regarding the lingua franca status of this language.

As to the experienced teachers, they do not seem to be ready to accept the shift in the position of English in today's rapidly changing world. This might be due to the fact that they cannot easily abandon their standard English oriented teaching practices that they have made use of over many years and received their authorities as English teachers. In other words, their long-term engagement with teaching standard English norms can be the underlying cause of their hesitations in terms of acknowledging current position of English as a global lingua franca. Another explanation for experienced teachers' ambivalent attitude towards the concept of ELF might be the fear of losing the authority they have received from teaching standard English norms over a number of years (Mahboob, 2003).

Moreover, the third research question of this study examined the inclusive perceptions of less experienced and experienced EFL teachers towards the pedagogical implications of ELF in view of its subcategories (English teachers (native and non-native), target language culture, global cultures, and English exams) in the research question four. Within this framework, the results did not indicate any major disagreements between these two groups of teachers. In conjunction with this, both the less experienced and the experienced teachers exhibit a neutral attitude towards the pedagogical implications of ELF considering the above mentioned factors. It seems like EFL teachers are confused about the concepts of EFL and ELF; hence, they cannot really distinguish between the two due to their longstanding commitment to standard English ideology (Seidlhofer, 2001).

Coexistence of both the EFL and ELF paradigms in teachers' minds seem to place them in a dilemma regarding the pedagogical implications of ELF. Furthermore, some broader sociocultural and sociopolitical realities of teachers' local contexts in accordance with English instruction might be another reason underlying EFL teachers' ambivalence. To illustrate, since passing a test is still considered to be the primary indicator of learning English in many EFL contexts, teachers continue to conduct a test-oriented teaching so as to be considered successful in their careers (Soruç, 2020). Moreover, considering standard English norms hence the native English teachers as the benchmark for competence is still prevalent in the ELT market (Wang, 2012). However, emerging realities of English language, on the other hand, forcing EFL teachers to reconsider their conceptualizations regarding EFL and reorient themselves towards ELF.

Further reason for less experienced and experienced English teachers' hesitation towards the pedagogical implications of ELF might be resulting from their concerns about lack of teaching and learning materials arranged specifically for that purpose. Justifiably, lack of ELF-aligned teaching pedagogy concerns EFL teachers as opposed to the ample amount of materials and methodology promoting standard English pedagogy (Sifakis & Bayyurt, 2018). All this data indicate that teachers seem to have quite a few reasons hindering their endorsement of the classroom practices of ELF. Given the fact that teachers' ambivalence regarding the instructional allegations of ELF is associated with the broader sociocultural and sociopolitical context, this situation is not likely to change in a short while unless the necessary support is provided by the relevant stakeholders and educational policy makers (Cogo, 2012; Jenkins & Wingate, 2015; Seidlhofer, 2011).

Along the same line, Young and Walsh (2010) state that EFL teachers have a positive approach towards ELF as a concept, yet still they have reservations on its pedagogical applications. Likewise, Suzuki (2011) specifies that even if less experienced teachers express their consciousness of various Englishes, they are still in favor of American and British varieties for teaching and learning purposes. Similarly, Cogo and Dewey (2012) and Jenkins (2007) maintain that although EFL teachers endorse ELF as a concept, they oppose the classroom implementations of it. Along the same line, Sarandi (2020) maintained that in-service English teachers did not have a uniform attitude towards the issues concerning ELF. However, the results of this study revealed that both the less experienced and the experienced teachers tend to be neutral towards applying ELF in their classrooms. Therefore, given the fact that people's perceptions are always in a state of flux, the teachers' neutrality might be the indication of progressive conceptual transition in favor of the pedagogical implications of ELF.

Conclusion and Implications

This study aimed at investigating EFL teachers' perceptions towards ELF and its pedagogical implications in relation to their years of teaching experience e.g. less experienced (1-5) and experienced (over 5). To begin with, the results revealed a noteworthy difference between the observations of these two groups of teachers towards ELF as a concept. Within this context, less experienced EFL teachers had a more positive attitude towards ELF as a phenomenon than the experienced EFL teachers. Namely, less experienced English teachers were stronger advocates of becoming familiar with unorthodox Englishes, prioritizing intelligibility over correctness, and focusing on international use of English as a learning objective rather than standard English norms. It can be concluded that less experienced teachers seem to be better informed about the changing status of English as a global lingua franca. As for the differences in the perceptions held by less experienced and experienced English teachers towards the pedagogical implications of ELF, the results did not manifest any major divergences between two groups. Put it differently, both groups of teachers seem to have some reservations against the applicability of ELF viewpoint in English classroom. Prevailing influence of widely acknowledged EFL paradigm seems to be the leading cause for their hesitation.

However, a gradual change is still likely to take place if teachers' awareness of ELF is raised. Only if today's EFL teachers can comprehend the contemporary status English, they can better inform their student regarding this issue (Deniz, Özkan, & Bayyurt, 2016). To this end, present investigation has some consequences for EFL teachers with reference to revisiting their views about the existing situation of English as a worldwide lingua franca. Firstly, it should be pointed out that English cannot be deemed as a

foreign language linked solely with the countries where it is utilized as a mother tongue. In that sense, teaching English from an EFL perspective no longer serves the needs of present-day learners since it is not learned just to interact with native English speakers. What is more, native speakers cannot be approached as single arbiters of this language on the grounds of its increasing role as international lingua franca. Therefore, EFL teachers need to pay heed to the constantly transforming socio-linguistic needs of their learners in today's interconnected world and adjust their theoretical and methodological approaches to these changes.

Moreover, ELT programs should encourage trainee teachers to reflect on their taken-for-granted native speaker oriented theoretical and practical assumptions about English language teaching (Sifakis, 2007; Seidlhofer, 2011). In this way, they can hold a critical view of underlying assumptions of standard English ideology which is known to promote either American or British English as a teaching model. Also, these programs should train and encourage preservice EFL teachers to think through their conventional teaching manners. Therefore, they can go beyond mainstream ELT pedagogy by noticing the contextual features of English language training. All in all, teacher training programs should equip pre-service teachers of English with necessary skills enabling them to move beyond the conventional ELT approach prioritizing standard English ideology and accuracy in the use of English in language training. Taking into account that the global status of English appears in all kinds of ways in numerous situations, experienced EFL teachers need to be in an ongoing effort to update their knowledge about the evolving character of this language. For that reason, there might be a need for them to attend seminars, meetings, practicums and ongoing formations in order to keep themselves informed with this dynamism. According to a study conducted by Bayyurt and Sifakis (2015), when EFL teachers are adequately informed about the developments of globality of English and its pedagogical allegations, they tend to acknowledge its significance and act accordingly in their teaching practices.

As for the limitations of this study, since this study was conducted in a single private university, the results can be generalized just for comparable education environments. However, the findings are likely to provide some additional data to the relevant literature which is tertiary level English language education. Secondly, the number of survey items (16 in total) were limited in this study which can be increased in the future studies. Moreover, in this particular study, only hard data were utilized to investigate the perceptions of EFL teachers, but qualitative data can also be included in future studies so as to gain a deeper understanding of the perceptions of EFL teachers in this regard (Strauss & Corbin, 2015). All in all, mixing methods in the forth-coming studies would provide a great support to the revelation of the participants' considerations of ELF. To conclude, in the future studies, less experienced and experienced EFL teachers can be observed in their classrooms in order to explore their perceptions of ELF through their classroom practices.

Acknowledgments

This article is part of the author's dissertation study.

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Genişletilmiş Özet

İngilizcenin uluslararası bir iletişim dili olmasına dair (ELF) paradigma bu dilin statüsünün algılanışına ve pedagojisine ilişkin bazı değişikliklere gidilmesi gerektiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Bu değişiklikleri sınıfa aktaracak olan başlıca aktörler de İngilizce öğretmenleridir. Dolayısıyla onların tüm bu gelişmeler hakkındaki algıları kritik bir önem arz etmektedir. Bu çerçevede bu araştırma deneyimli ve az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin ELF ve onun pedagojik sonuçlarına dair algılarını karşılaştırmalı olarak incelemiştir. Veriler, uygun örnekleme yoluyla seçilen 32 az deneyimli ve 20 deneyimli İngilizce öğretmeninden nicel araştırma yöntemi kullanılarak toplanmıştır. Araştırmada kullanılan anket araştırmacı tarafından ilgili literatür taranarak hazırlanmış ve SPSS 25 kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir.

Az deneyimli (1-5 yıl) ve deneyimli (5 yılın üzerinde) İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İngilizcenin uluslararası ortak iletişim dili (ELF) olmasına yönelik algıları bağımsız örneklem t-test ile analiz edilmiştir. Sonuçlar, mesleki deneyimleri açısından bakıldığında bu iki öğretmen grubunun ELF'e yönelik algıları arasında önemli farklılıklar olduğunu göstermektedir. Bu durumu ifade eden ilgili p değeri 0.05'in altındadır ($p = .002$). Bu verilere bakıldığında, en fazla beş yıllık öğretmenlik tecrübesine sahip İngilizce öğretmenlerinin, İngilizcenin hayatın birçok alanında ortak iletişim dili olması statüsü nedeniyle, İngiliz dilinin kullanımındaki farklılaşmalara karşı daha kabullenici olma eğiliminde oldukları söylenebilir.

Aynı şekilde deneyimli ve az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin ELF'in pedagojik yansımalarına yönelik algıları bağımsız örneklem t-test uygulanarak analiz edilmiştir. Veriler deneyimli ve az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin algıları arasında bu bakımdan önemli bir fark olmadığını ortaya çıkarmıştır. Bu sonuç ile ilişkili olarak p değeri 0.05'in üzerinde çıkmıştır ($p = .432$). Bu açıdan bakıldığında ELF'in pedagojik etkileri söz konusu olduğunda hem deneyimli hem de az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin tereddütlü oldukları sonucu ortaya çıkmıştır. Diğer bir deyişle, İngilizce öğretmenleri, öğretmenlik kariyerlerindeki deneyimlerinden bağımsız olarak, sınıf içi pedagojik uygulamalarında anadili İngilizce normlardan vazgeçme konusunda kararsız olduklarını ortaya koymuşlardır.

Sonuç olarak bulgular az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İngilizcenin uluslararası bir iletişim dili olması statüsüne dair daha fazla farkındalığa sahip olduklarını ortaya koymuştur. Diğer yandan, bu kavramın pedagojik sonuçlarının sınıf içinde uygulanmasına gelindiğinde, hem deneyimli hem de az deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenleri kararsız bir tutum sergilemişlerdir. Ancak bu sonuçlar gene de göstermektedir ki, öğretmenlerin ELF konusundaki farkındalığı artırılırsa, kademeli bir değişimin gerçekleşmesi muhtemeldir. Bunun olabilmesi için de İngilizce öğretmenleri İngilizcenin çağdaş statüsünü kavrayabilmeleri ve bunu öğrencilerine aktarabilmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu düzlemde, bu araştırmanın İngilizce öğretmenlerine yönelik bazı bazı sonuçları vardır. Öncelikle, İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İngilizceyi anadili İngilizce normlarını merkez alarak öğretmeleri artık günümüz öğrencilerinin ihtiyaçlarını karşılamamaktadır. Bunun da başlıca sebebi öğrencilerin bu dili sadece ana dili İngilizce olan kişilerle iletişim kurmak için öğrenmiyor olmalarıdır. Dolayısıyla, İngilizce öğretmenlerinin günümüzün küreselleşen dünyasında öğrencilerinin sürekli değişen ihtiyaçlarını dikkate almaları ve bu ihtiyaçlara cevap verecek yaklaşımları geliştirebilmeleri gerekmektedir. Bu anlamda İngilizce öğretmenlerine hem lisans eğitimi düzeyinde hem de lisans eğitimi sonrasında ilgili kurumlar tarafından gerekli destek sunulmalıdır.